

TRANSITIONING FROM SWIDDEN CULTIVATION TO AGROFORESTRY: A CASE STUDY REPORT ON FARMING SYSTEMS IN LA UNION, PHILIPPINES

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ABSTRACT

This case study investigates the extent of agroforestry adoption and explores the reasons why upland farmers in La Union, Philippines have transitioned from Swidden cultivation to agroforestry farming systems. The study utilizes secondary data from the research outputs of students at the Don Mariano Marcos Memorial State University (DMMMSU). Baseline information on Swidden farming practices was sourced from Atty. Benjamin B. Sapitula's 1995 dissertation, "Sustainability of Swidden Farms in Selected Uplands of La Union, Philippines." Data on agroforestry adoption were collected from selected undergraduate and graduate theses of the College of Agroforestry and Forestry, DMMMSU-NLUC, Bacnotan, La Union, spanning from 2017 to 2020. The findings indicate that Swidden farming was still prevalent in La Union in 1995. However, due to the unsustainable and environmentally destructive nature of Swidden farming, farmers began seeking alternatives and subsequently adopted agroforestry. Interviews with 264 farmers, documented in three theses, revealed that all respondents have integrated agroforestry practices into their farms and Community-Based Forest Management (CBFM) areas. Farmers adopted agroforestry as a sustainable alternative to slash-and-burn cultivation for several reasons. They believe agroforestry reduces soil erosion, improves soil and water quality, restores vegetative cover, increases land productivity, and provides a sustainable income. Additionally, farmers are employing various soil and water conservation measures, such as alley cropping, multiple cropping, terracing,

reforestation, water harvesting, diversion canals, and mulching, to maintain and enhance the environmental conditions of their farms.

Keywords: *Agroforestry, CBFM, Soil and water conservation, Swidden cultivation*

INTRODUCTION

Forests play a crucial role in sustaining life on Earth by meeting nearly all of humanity's basic needs, including providing a wholesome environment. Rainforests, in particular, are vital for maintaining biodiversity, which is essential for the survival of all life forms. Ecological theory suggests that diversity is linked to stability, indicating that ecosystems with a wide variety of species are more stable than those dominated by a single species, such as in monoculture systems (Sapitula, 1995).

Ten thousand years ago, 57% of the world's habitable land, equivalent to six billion hectares, was covered by forests. Today, only four billion hectares remain, indicating that the world has lost one-third of its forests—an area twice the size of the United States. By 1950, agricultural land almost equaled forested land, constituting 43% of habitable land. By 2018, agricultural land had increased to 46%, while forest cover had decreased to 38%. Contrary to popular belief, the growing pressures on land from modern populations are not primarily due to sprawling megacities, which occupy just 1% of global habitable land. Instead, humanity's largest impact on land use is driven by agriculture and food production (Ritchie, 2021).

The Union of Concerned Scientists (UCS) reports that just four commodities are responsible for tropical deforestation: beef, soy, palm oil and wood products. UCS estimates that an area the size of Switzerland (14,800 square miles, or 38,300 square km) is lost to deforestation every year. Natural fires in tropical forests tend to be rare but intense. Human-lit fires are commonly used to clear land for agricultural use. First, valuable timber is harvested, then the remaining vegetation is burned to make way for crops like soy or cattle grazing. In 2019, the number of human-lit fires in Brazil skyrocketed. As of August 2019, more than 80,000 fires burned in the Amazon, an increase of almost 80% from 2018, National Geographic reported. Many forests are cleared to make way for palm oil plantations. Palm oil is the most commonly produced vegetable oil and is found in half of all supermarket products. It is cheap, versatile and can be added to both food and personal products like lipsticks and shampoo. Its popularity has spurred people to clear tropical forests to grow more palm trees. Growing the trees that produce the oil requires the leveling of native forest and the destruction of local peatlands — which doubles the harmful effect on the ecosystem. According to a report published by Zion Market Research, the global palm oil market was valued at \$65.73 billion in 2015 and is expected to reach \$92.84 billion in 2021 (Derouin, 2019).

Worldwide deforestation is threatening the stability and existence of the world's remaining forests. Today, most deforestation is happening in the tropics. Areas that were inaccessible in the past are now within reach as new roads are constructed through the dense forests. Often, deforestation occurs when forested area is cut and cleared to make way for agriculture or grazing. Unfortunately, swidden cultivation and expansion of agricultural lands have been identified as the major causes of deforestation.

Swidden agriculture, also known as shifting cultivation, refers to a technique of rotational farming in which land is cleared for cultivation commonly with the use of fire and then left and vacated to reinvigorate after few years' time. Swidden agriculture or slash-and-burn farming is a widespread subsistence practice in the tropics (Peng et al. 2014; Schuck et al. 2002). Swidden is mainly practiced in the mountainous and hilly parts of Latin America, Central Africa and Southeast Asia by smallholder farmers, and often drives deforestation as well as forest degradation (Rahman et al, 2016).

In the Philippines, the practice is more commonly known as "kaingin" making and that farmers call their cultivated farms as "kaingin" areas. Swiddening may be defined as an agricultural system which is characterized by a rotation of fields rather of crops by short period of cropping (one to three years) alternating with long fallow periods (up to twenty and more years) and by clearing through burning (Sapitula, 1995).

In order to overcome the negative consequences of deforestation and swidden farming, farmers would need to adopt new practices that serve multiple purposes including conserving forest resources as well as producing food and supporting sustainable development (Rahman et al, 2016).

Agroforestry, and specifically the practice of growing trees on farmland alongside crops, has well-established research evidence of its potential to reduce deforestation and forest degradation at a landscape scale. One definition of agroforestry is 'a dynamic, ecologically-based, natural resources management system that, through the integration of trees on farms and in the agricultural landscape, diversifies and sustains production for increased social, economic and environmental benefits for land users at all levels (Rahman et al, 2016).

As cited by Mapili (2019), Agroforestry has been used as a major strategy to enjoin forest occupants to become partners in rehabilitating degrading forestland. As an alternative to the destructive kaingin-making or slash- and- burn farming of most farmers, agroforestry was expected to reduce soil erosion, improve soil quality, restore vegetative cover, increase land productivity, and uplift farmers' level of living through sustained farm income and productivity.

The main purpose of this case study is to document the extent of agroforestry adoption and perceive various reasons behind why upland farmers in La Union, Philippines have shifted Swidden cultivation into agroforestry farming system.

METHODOLOGY

Materials and methods

Data Collection

Secondary data were collected using research outputs of students at the Don Mariano Marcos Memorial State University. Data on Swidden Farming were obtained from the Dissertation of Atty. Benjamin B. Sapitula dated March 1995 entitled “Sustainability of Swidden Farms in Selected Uplands of La Union, Philippines. This study was used as the baseline of information for swidden farming practices in the province.

Meanwhile, data on Agroforestry adoption were collected from selected undergraduate and graduate theses of the College of Agroforestry and Forestry, DMMMSU-NLUC, Bacnotan, La Union from 2017-2020. This includes results of the study of Ms. Ruby Anne G. Olbinaldo entitled Analysis of Gender Participation in the Implementation of Community- Based Forest Management Program in Aringay and Pugo , La Union (2018), Soil and Water Conservation Practices in the Upland Communities of San Gabriel, La Union: A Response to Climate Change Mitigation by Mr. Noel G. Gadoy (2017) and the study on Gender Participation in the Sustainable Management of Resources Within Upland Agroforests in La Union, Philippines (202) by Ms. Lieslea M. Wagayen.

Aforementioned dissertation/thesis books were borrowed from the College of Agroforestry and Forestry Library.

Table 1. Distribution of Respondents per Study Title and Location

Study Title	Number of Adopter/ Location	Percentage (%)
A. Swidden Farming		
Sustainability of Swidden Farms in Selected Uplands of La Union Philippines (1995)	19 out of 187 families (Cares, Pugo)	10.16%
	18 out of 37 families (Amontok, San Gabriel)	48.65%
SubTotal:	37	58.81%
B. Agroforestry		
Analysis of Gender Participation of Community-Based Forest	26 respondents (Macabato, Aringay)	100%

Management Program in Aringay and Pugo, La Union (2018)	33 respondents (Cares, Pugo)	100%
Soil and Water Conservation Practices 100% in the Upland Communities of San Gabriel, La Union: A Response to Climate Change Mitigation (2017)	60 respondents (Brgys. Balbalayang, Daking, Lipa Norte, and Polipol)	
Gender participation in the Sustainable Management of Resources Within Upland Agroforests in La Union, Philippines	50 respondents (Arosip, Bacnotan)	100%
	70 respondents (Casilagan, Naguilian)	100%
100%	25 respondents (Lacong, San Gabriel)	
SubTotal	264	100%
GrandTotal	301	

Figure 1. Locale of the Study

Analysis of Data

The data gathered were collated according to the objectives of the study and were analyzed statistically. With regards to the data on swidden farming, two municipalities were included such as Cares, Pugo, La Union and Amontok, San Gabriel, La Union. The following variables were used as indicators of swidden farming sustainability within the study sites:

- 1) PSPP- Present Productivity Period in years
- 2) PSFP- Present Fallow Period in Years

To determine the level of swidden's sustainability, the following set of criteria were used:

1. Productivity Period in years

0-2 - Not Sustainable

2-4 - Sustainable (low)

4-6 - Sustainable (average)

More than 6 - Sustainable (high)

2. Fallow Period in year

More than 2 - Not Sustainable

1-2 - Sustainable (low)

0-1 - Sustainable (moderate)

Negative to 0- Sustainable (high)

Conversely, the data on Agroforestry adoption, descriptive quantitative, and range of values were used in the interpretation of data as shown below.

Numerical Values	Range Values	Descriptive Rating
5	4.20-5.0	Very Highly Adopted
4	3.40-4.19	Highly Adopted
3	2.60-3.39	Moderately Adopted
2	1.80-2.59	Fairly Adopted
1	1.00-1.79	Not Adopted

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2 shows the distribution of respondents who practiced swidden farming as of March 1995. A total of 37 farmers are practicing kaingin system which is equivalent to 58.81%.

Based on the pronouncement of upland farmers in the study sites, they practice swiddening because it seems to be the only alternative to provide them their needs for cash and food. In fact, most of them declared that swiddening required too much labor and no matter how much care is observed during the clearing process, destruction of forest ecosystem cannot be avoided. Trees, vines, shrubs and other forms of plants within the swidden area had to be cut, to be burned later, thereby decreasing the biodiversity in the particular site, consequently decreasing the stability of the ecosystem. The stability of the site can be brought back or restored depending on the cropping system practiced by the farmer.

Table 2. Distribution of Respondents Who Practiced Swidden Farming

Study Title	Number of Adopter/Percentage Location (%)
Sustainability of Swidden Farms In Selected Uplands of La Union Philippines (1995)	19 out of 187 families (Cares, Pugo) 10.16%
	18 out of 37 families 2753

	(Amontok, San Gabriel)	48.65%
Total	37	58.81%

Swiddening as practiced in the study sites is similar to shifting cultivation as practiced in other parts of the country. The only differences are the burning of unburned branches and litters termed as “Keang” and have relatively shorter fallow period of 2-5 years. Eight (8) variables significantly affect the sustainability of swidden farms according to Sapitula, 1995. These are the crop structure, permanent use of the swidden, crop protection problems, number of soil conservation techniques, present diversity of crops, use of crop residues, and the predicted density of crops.

There seems to be more people who look at the negative aspects of swidden farming than those who think positively and are putting much blame on the swiddenists/swidden farmers. It would be unfair to the latter to generalize such statements because there are also indications that swidden farms of indigenous people/tribes are sustainable. Sapitula (1995) cited that the real issue on the practice of swidden cultivation is its sustainability. The unsustainable practice of shifting cultivation represents the biggest threat to the future rainforests.

Haphazard procedure involving an almost negligible minimum of labor output and it is basically simple and uncomplicated, and cheap yet effective way for the farmers to clear the land and add nutrients to the soil are some of the advantages of swidden farming but it works only for a short term, but the long term effects include deforestation, pollution and a tremendous carbon footprint Belsky (1993).

Likewise, the study of Dove (2008) on the Iban agriculture in Borneo illustrates that while shifting cultivation has several ecological and cultural benefits, it faces significant challenges in terms of sustainability under increased population pressure and economic demands. Transitioning to continuous cultivation can offer more stable economic benefits and higher productivity but requires overcoming substantial socio-cultural and environmental challenges. This balanced perspective highlights the complexity of managing traditional agricultural practices in the face of modern pressures and environmental sustainability concerns.

Moreover, the study by Mertz et al. (2008) provides a nuanced view of shifting cultivation, highlighting both its advantages and disadvantages. One of the primary benefits is the role shifting cultivation plays in maintaining soil fertility and biodiversity. When fallow periods are managed well, the practice can contribute to ecological balance and the regeneration of forest areas. The study also suggests that shifting cultivation can be a sustainable land use system when local governance is strong and external inputs, like fertilizers, are used

appropriately to enhance productivity. The researchers conclude that while shifting cultivation has potential benefits, its success and sustainability largely depend on appropriate management practices and supportive local governance structures. They advocate for integrating modern agricultural techniques with traditional practices to enhance the system's sustainability

The government has acknowledged the importance of addressing the well-being of upland inhabitants and has recognized the need to involve them as partners in forest protection and conservation. Currently, government efforts are concentrated on developing approaches and alternatives to Swidden cultivation, aiming to promote sustainable land use and enhance forest conservation.

Table 3. Distribution of Respondents Who Practiced Agroforestry

Study Title	Number of Adopter/ Location	Percentage (%)
Analysis of Gender Participation of Community-Based Forest Management Program in Aringay and Pugo, La Union (2018)	26 respondents (Macabato,	100%
	33 respondents (Cares, Pugo)	100%
Soil and Water Conservation Practices in the Upland Communities of San Gabriel, La Union: A Response to Polipol) Climate Change Mitigation (2017)	60 respondents (Brgys. Balbalayang, Daking, Lipay Norte, and	100%
Gender participation in the Sustainable Management of Resources in the Upland Agroforests in La Union, Philippines (2020)	50 respondents (Arosip, Bacnotan)	100%
	70 respondents (Casilagan, Naguilian)	100%
	25 respondents (Lacong, San Gabriel)	100%
Total	264	100%

Table 3 presents the distribution of respondents who practiced agroforestry in their farms. A total number of 264 respondents from various municipalities of La Union were interviewed and documented from 2017-2020 and resulted to 100% adoption of Agroforestry farming system within their own farms and/or under the Community Based Forest Management Agreement of the government specifically the Department of Environment and Natural Resources (DENR).

Community-Based Forest Management (CBFM) often results in numerous positive impacts, including improved forest conservation and rehabilitation. Local communities, having a direct stake in the health and productivity of their forests, tend to adopt sustainable practices that enhance biodiversity and prevent deforestation. Economic benefits for the community members also arise through the creation of livelihoods tied to forest products and eco-tourism. Additionally, CBFM programs typically lead to stronger community cohesion and empowerment, as locals are involved in decision-making processes and capacity-building activities. These benefits collectively contribute to the long-term sustainability and resilience of forest ecosystems (Sayer, 2015).

According to Olbinaldo (2018), a primary objective of Community-Based Forest Management (CBFM) is the sustainable management of forestlands and resources by upland communities. The sustainability of these forests depends on effectively mobilizing upland residents to actively engage in resource management. CBFM promotes ongoing preservation, protection, management, and rehabilitation of forestlands, fostering a collaborative approach to forest sustainability (Natan, 2018). Additionally, Resosudarmo (2003) found that CBFM leads to significant improvements in forest conservation and biodiversity, particularly in areas where local governance structures are robust.

Plate 1. Agroforestry System (integration of trees, crops and animals) in Arosip, Bacnotan, La Union (Wagayen, 2020).

Plate 2. Multiple Cropping and Intercropping in Barangay Lacong, San Gabriel, La Union (Wagayen, 2020)

Plate 3. Multiple cropping (Cacao-Guyabano-Coffee-Papaya and Banana) in Bacnotan, La Union (Wagayen, 2020)

Plate 4. Mulching in a Papaya Plantation as SWC Practice at San Gabriel, La Union (Gadoy, 2017).

Plate 5. Rice Terracing- One of the SWC Practices at Pugo, La Union (Olbinaldo, 2018).

It has been known that these respondents are also practicing different Soil and Water Conservation measures like alley cropping, multiple cropping, terracing, reforestation, establishment of water harvester, diversion canal and mulching in order to protect and preserve good environmental conditions of their farms (Wagayen, 2020).

Conservation of soil and water resources is important for sustainability of agriculture and environment. Soil and water resources are under immense pressure due to ever increasing population thereby ensuing growing demand for food, fiber and shelter (Smith et al., 2020). Soil and water resources are being deteriorated due to different anthropogenic and natural factors. Soil erosion is one of the several major deteriorative processes which results in deterioration of the soil. Soil erosion is removal of soil due to movement of water and/or air. Soil erosion may lead to the significant loss of soil productivity and thus may lead to the desertification under sever conditions. Water and wind are the major agencies which are responsible of soil erosion. Deforestation, over-grazing, intensive cultivation, mismanagement of cultivated soils and intensive urbanization are major factors triggering the soil erosion. For sustainable agriculture and environment, it is pertinent to protect the soil resources against erosion. Different control measures should be adopted to protect the soil resources against erosion. The concept of soil conservation cannot be materialized without conserving and efficient use of water resources. It is therefore pre-requisite that soil conservation practices should be adopted. Soil conservation practice include soil management, crop management, engineering, range management and forestry operation (Bashir, et al, 2017).

In a study on coping strategies and perceptions of farmers regarding the roles of trees in climate change mitigation and adaptation in the upland barangays of Bacnotan, La Union, Fontanilla (2016) found that farmers have already adopted integrated farming and agroforestry practices, incorporating fruit and forest trees with other crops, vegetables, and livestock. The upland farmers in Bacnotan, La Union have implemented various coping strategies, including diversified farming/cropping, planting drought-resistant crops, employing soil and water conservation methods, utilizing improved post-harvest technology, applying mulching, and enhancing irrigation systems.

Table 4. Reasons Why Farmers Shifted Swidden Cultivation to Agroforestry

Limitations of Swidden Cultivation	Advantages of Agroforestry
Cheap and effective way for the farmers to clear the land and add nutrients to the soil. It works only for a short term, but the long term effects include deforestation, pollution and a tremendous carbon footprint.	<p>Economic: Provision of diverse products and poverty reduction</p> <p>Low input of agrochemicals</p> <p>Agroforestry systems may also create opportunities for small-scale forest-based enterprises.</p> <p>Reduce rural poverty by increasing on-farm production and household income</p>
No crop rotation in swidden agriculture	<p>Social: Maximizing output per labour input</p> <p>Help improve the health and nutrition of the rural poor</p>
Destructive and leads to soil Erosion and land	Prevention of run off and better water management
Permanent loss of forest cover resulting from re-clearing a once-used	Soil fertility and closed nutrient cycles
Not sustainable	Prevention of damage to forests
	Climate change mitigation
	Aesthetic value
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Shifting Cultivation as Forest Violation -Creation of forest departments - Designation of Forest Guards, and -The rise of conservation and protection policies. 	

Table 4 shows the limitations/ disadvantages of swidden cultivation that mainly drives the farmers shifting swidden farming to Agroforestry. There are three (3) major benefits of Agroforestry as cited at FAO (2018). These are economic benefits, social benefits and environmental benefits. In the economic benefits, most agroforestry systems aim to increase or maintain the production and productivity of farming systems; reduce agricultural inputs and thus production costs; and diversify production by the use of trees or other woody perennials to produce, for example, food, fodder, lumber, building materials and woodfuel. Agroforestry systems may also create opportunities for small-

scale forest-based enterprises.

Agroforestry can help reduce rural poverty by increasing on-farm production and household income and by providing employment opportunities, and it can reduce the risk of economic failure by increasing the diversity of production within farming systems. Social benefits of agroforestry on the other hand, may help increase in production, productivity and product diversity through agroforestry can help improve the health and nutrition of the rural poor. The on-farm production of fuel, fodder and other tree products, otherwise collected from off-farm sources, can reduce the time and effort needed to obtain them (often lessening the burden on women) or save money if the products would otherwise be purchased (Franzel et al., 2001). When the supply of labor changes at the household or community level (e.g. due to the seasonal out-migration of men), agroforestry offers options for maximizing output per labour input. The perpetuation of traditional agroforestry practices can help maintain social bonds established through mutual- help arrangements (e.g. in the case of shifting cultivation). And the environmental benefit of Agroforestry system is to provide a range of environmental services. For example, they can improve soil fertility, protect crops and livestock from wind, restore degraded lands, improve water conservation, limit pests and prevent soil erosion. If properly designed and managed, agroforestry systems can contribute to biodiversity conservation and climate-change adaptation and mitigation. If deployed inadequately, however, they may lead to decreases in production because of competition among trees and crops. From the three major benefits of Agroforestry, we may also include the aesthetic value or forms of recreation. Agroforestry farms could create a place for recreational activities and meditation. It could also be promoted as agro-ecotourism or leisure parks for amusement and relaxation (Nair, 2001).

One of the recommendations of Sapitula (1995) in his study was the incorporation of planting perennial crops to their agricultural crops since planting of annuals like cereals and vegetables is not a sustainable production system for swidden farms. Thus, agroforestry system should be promoted and kaingin making should be discouraged.

Aside from various disadvantages of swidden farming as discussed earlier, our government is also prompt in crafting laws with regards to forest protection and conservation. Under the Presidential Decree No. 705 Section 38 (Control of Concession Area) says that in order to achieve the effective protection of the forest lands and the resources thereof from illegal entry, unlawful occupation, kaingin, fire, insect infestation, theft, and other forms of forest destruction, the utilization of timber therein shall not be allowed except through license agreements under which the holders thereof shall have the exclusive privilege to cut all the allowable harvestable timber in their respective concessions, and the additional right of occupation, possession, and control over the same, to the exclusive of all others, except the government, but with the corresponding obligation to adopt all the protection and conservation measures to ensure the continuity of the productive condition of said areas, conformably with multiple use and sustained yield management. Thus, activities such as illegal and excessive cutting of trees, kaingin making, forest squatting were unlawful acts and have corresponding penalties and charges from the government.

Smith et al. (2023) conducted a comprehensive examination of agroforestry, highlighting its multifaceted benefits. By integrating trees into agricultural landscapes, agroforestry emerges as a powerful tool for conservation and sustainability. The study underscores its contributions to biodiversity conservation, soil health enhancement, carbon sequestration, and effective water resource management.

Moreover, the economic advantages of agroforestry are emphasized, demonstrating its potential to boost crop yields, diversify income streams, and lower input costs for farmers. Additionally, the research delves into the social dimensions, revealing how agroforestry fosters improved livelihoods, enhances community resilience, and preserves cultural heritage. This holistic perspective underscores agroforestry's potential as a sustainable land use strategy, addressing ecological, economic, and social challenges in agricultural systems.

Conclusions

Swidden cultivation also called slash and burn, kaingin making, and shifting cultivation was extremely practiced by upland farmers in the past in most Asian countries including the Philippines. In 1995, it was documented that swidden farming was also practiced in the Province of La Union. However, too often, swidden cultivation was perceived and once thought as extremely destructive, exploiting and unsustainability of the system has been the cause to deforestation. Some authors considered some of the advantages of swidden farming like cheap and effective way for the farmers to clear the land and add nutrients to the soil. It works only for a short term, but the long-term effects include deforestation, pollution, and a tremendous carbon footprint. One way or another, it has good effects, but in the long run farmer practitioners and even the government discovered the bad and harmful effects of doing such practice. Because of this, farmers opted to find alternatives and ways to elucidate swidden farming. Nowadays, Agroforestry farming system has been greatly adopted in the province of La Union. Most upland farmers are practicing this because they strongly believe that this is far better than their old practice which is the kaingin system.

Recommendations

Some farmers acknowledged the advantages of Agroforestry but some of them also declared that this practice needs technical know-how since it is knowledge and technology-intensive. So, to further improve the knowledge and skills in agroforestry technology, there is a need to conduct seminars and trainings or by creating demonstration projects showcasing the system. There is still a lot more to discover about Agroforestry, but considering its advantageous effects for now, may we then appreciate the technology and look for its further contributions into Filipino farmers' lives and the environment we dwell in.

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Furthermore, the author acknowledge the contributions of the undergraduate and graduate students from the College of Agroforestry and Forestry, DMMMSU-NLUC, Bacnotan, La Union, whose theses spanning from 2017 to 2020 provided essential insights into agroforestry adoption in the region. In particular, the works of Ms. Ruby Anne G. Olbinaldo, Mr. Noel G. Gadoy, and Ms. Lieslea M. Wagayen, including their studies on Gender Participation in the Implementation of Community-Based Forest Management, Soil and Water Conservation Practices, and Sustainable Management of Resources within Upland Agroforests in La Union, Philippines, significantly enriched the research.

Their dedication and scholarly endeavors have greatly facilitated the advancement of knowledge in the field of farming systems and land management practices in the region.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study, "Transitioning from Swidden Cultivation to Agroforestry: A Case Study Report on Farming Systems in La Union, Philippines," was conducted in compliance with ethical standards. The research utilized secondary data obtained from undergraduate and master's theses from the Don Mariano Marcos Memorial State University (DMMMSU). The secondary data included in this study were originally collected and documented by students under proper academic supervision, ensuring adherence to ethical guidelines for data collection and analysis. All sources of data have been appropriately cited to acknowledge the contributions of the original authors. No primary data collection involving human participants was conducted for this study, thereby eliminating the need for additional ethical clearance specific to this research. The study aims to respect and uphold the integrity of the original data and the academic work of the students whose theses were utilized.

REFERENCES

- Bashir et al. 2017. Soil and Water Conservation. Assessed at https://www.researchgate.net/publication/320729156_Soil_and_Water_Conservation on April 1, 2024.
- Belsky, J. 1993. Household food security, farm trees and agroforestry: A comparative study in Indonesia and the Philippines. *Human Organization* 52:130-141.

- Carig, E.T. (2012). Impact Assessment of Community-Based Forest Management in the Philippines: A case study of CBFM Sites in Nueva Viscaya. ICMSS' 2012, Penang, Malaysia.
- Derouin, S. (2019). Deforestation: Facts, Causes and Effects. Assessed at www.nationalgeographic.com/environment/article/deforestation on February 2, 2024.
- Dove, M. R. (1981). The transition from shifting cultivation to continuous cultivation: Local transformations of Iban agriculture, Borneo (Doctoral dissertation). Stanford University.
- Fontanilla, FE (2016). Coping Strategies and Perceptions of Farmers on the Roles of Trees in Climate Change Mitigation and Adoption in the Upland Barangays of Bacnotan, La Union. Graduate Thesis. DMMMSU-NLUC, Bacnotan, La Union.
- Franzel, S., Coe, R., & Cooper, P. J. M. (2001). Improving livelihoods through agroforestry: Case studies in Eastern Africa. *Agroforestry Systems*, 51(3), 257-273. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1010615402980>
- Gadoy, NG. (2017). Soil and Water Conservation Practices in the Upland Communities of San Gabriel, La Union: A response to Climate Change Mitigation. Undergraduate Thesis. DMMMSU-NLUC, Bacnotan, La Union.
- Hannah, R. (2021). The World has lost One-Third of its Forest, but an End of Deforestation is Possible. Assessed at ourworldindata.org/world-lost-one-third-forests on January 1, 2021.
- Mapili, L.M. (2019). Farmers Survey on the Soil and Water Conservation Practices of Ten Barangays in the Municipality of Naguilian, La Union. Undergraduate Thesis. DMMMSU-NLUC, Bacnotan, La Union.
- Mertz, O., Wadley, R. L., Christensen, A. E., Colfer, C. J. P., Müller, D., Bruce, T., ... & Leisz, S. J. (2008). A fresh look at shifting cultivation: Fallow length an uncertain indicator of productivity. *Agricultural Systems*, 96(1-3), 75-84. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agsy.2007.06.002>.
- Natan, C.P. (2018). Assessment on the Gender Participation in the Implementation of Community Based Forest Management Program at San Juan, La Union. Unpublished Undergraduate Thesis. DMMMSU-NLUC, Bacnotan, La Union.
- Nair, P. K. R. (2001). *An Introduction to Agroforestry*. Springer Science & Business Media.
- Olbinaldo, RAG. (2018). Analysis of Gender Participation in the Implementation of Community- Based Forest Management Program in Aringay and Pugo, La Union. Undergraduate Thesis. DMMMSU-NLUC, Bacnotan, La Union.
- Rahman, S. A., Sunderland, T. C., Roshetko, J. M., & Healey, J. R. (2016). Finding alternatives to swidden agriculture: Does agroforestry improve livelihood options and reduce pressure on existing forest? *Agroforestry Systems*, 90(5), 1-12
- Ritchie, H. (2021). Global land use: How the world uses its land. *Our World in Data*. Retrieved from <https://ourworldindata.org/land-use>.
- Resosudarmo, D. (2003). Forest governance and decentralization in Indonesia: Implications for community livelihoods (Doctoral dissertation). Australian National University.
- Sapitula, B.P. (1995). Sustainability of Swidden Farms in Selected Uplands of La Union Philippines. Thesis Dissertation. DMMMSU-NLUC, Bacnotan, La Union.

- Sayer, J. (2015). Sustainable forest management through community-based approaches. World Resources Institute. Retrieved from <https://www.wri.org/our-work/project/global-restoration-initiative/sustainable-forest-management>.
- Smith, J. A., & Johnson, R. B. (2020). Soil conservation practices and their impact on agricultural sustainability. *Journal of Soil and Water Conservation*, 75(3), 120-135.
- Wagayen, L. M. (2024). Gender Participation in the Sustainable management of Resources within Upland Agroforests in La union, Philippines. *Ignatian International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research*, 2(4), 1310–1357. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11046372>.